
**Beyond the Human Gaze: A Comparative Ecocritical Study of
Hardy's Wessex and VanderMeer's Area X**

Ms. Shiva Kamakshi Devi G. V.,

PhD Research Scholar,

PG Department & Research Centre of English,

The Standard Fireworks Rajaratnam College for
Women, Sivakasi.

Dr. B. Siva Priya,

Associate Professor,

PG Department & Research Centre of English,

The Standard Fireworks Rajaratnam College for
Women, Sivakasi.

Abstract

This paper explores how the fictional settings in literature can act as an important driving force that shapes the plot of the novel. It compares two very different fictional geographies, Thomas Hardy's Wessex and Jeff VanderMeer's Area X, to understand how nature is represented in each. While Hardy's Wessex is based on real places in Southwest England, it reflects the characters' emotions, inner turmoil, societal problems and the slow decline of rural life in the Victorian era. In contrast, VanderMeer's Area X is a mysterious place which decentres the human, transforms people and challenges their identity, science and nature itself. By comparing Wessex and Area X, this paper highlights how literature reflects changing attitudes towards nature and the environment. These fictional landscapes encourage readers to move beyond a human centered view of the world and to see nature as something active, alive, and interconnected with human life.

Keywords: Settings, Narrative agent, Social problems, Ecocritical, Interconnectedness.

Introduction

Throughout history, literature has explored the intricate relationship between people and their environment, seeing the environment as more than just a place; it is a powerful force that shapes perception, identity, and fate. Thomas Hardy's fictional Wessex and Jeff VanderMeer's Area X, are two distinct settings but thematically related landscapes that transcend their physical characteristics to play

important roles in the plot. Immersed in the Victorian era's rural realism, Hardy gives his imagined landscape agricultural cycles, seasonal changes, and moral significance to highlight the precarious position of human fate in relation to the natural world, either in harmony or conflict. VanderMeer, on the other hand, presents an ecocritical and posthuman viewpoint that reinterprets nature as a transformational, foreign force that transcends human comprehension and blurs the boundaries between the human and the environment. This comparative study explores how both writers produce fictional landscapes that speak to ecocritical concepts, looking at how location functions as a dynamic force that affects and overturns human existence in addition to providing a setting for action.

Thomas Hardy (1840–1928) was a prominent English novelist and poet during the Victorian era. Although Hardy had architectural training, he made literature his full-time career. Deep emotional conflicts, the impact of fate and the environment on human lives, and realistic portrayals of rural life are all hallmarks of his writings. *The Mayor of Casterbridge*, *Jude the Obscure*, *Far from the Madding Crowd*, and *Tess of the d'Urbervilles* are a few of his best-known works.

Jeff VanderMeer, born in 1968, is a contemporary American writer. He is recognized for his significant impact on speculative fiction, and eco-fiction. His series named *Southern Reach Trilogy*, explores themes of ecological transformation, mental unravelling, and the limits of human understanding, brought him widespread acclaim. His fiction questions traditional divides between the human and nonhuman, self and environment, as well as knowledge and ignorance, drawing heavily from Posthumanist and ecocritical perspectives. Some of his novels include *Veniss Underground*, *Shriek: An Afterword*, *Borne*, *Dead Astronauts* etc.

Imagined geography

One of the first things the authors confront while writing a novel is where to set it. Is it better to set a story in a real place or a fictional one? According to M.H. Abrams, the setting refers to the location, time, and social context in which all the actions unfold. He noted that in theatrical productions, the setting, also referred to as decoration, establishes the stage to represent a specific place. The setting acts as the backdrop of an event in prose, encompassing elements such as place, time, or incidents that serve both physical and psychological purposes. Apart from a mere background, a setting could be perceived as a dynamic, constructed element of a narrative and sometimes a lead of the story. According to Edward Soja, setting is a vital force that gives a shape to the novel, which can even propel a plot forward. “Coleridge’s imagination is able to “create” rather than merely resemble, by dissolving the fixities and definites the mental pictures or images, received from the sense and unifying them into a new whole” (Abrams 123), according to Coleridge, imagination reshapes and transforms sensory experiences into new, unified creations, rather than just making a faithful copy of a reality. Many writers over the years have preferred to create an imaginary setting. Because they believe that it gives them a sense of freedom to express their thoughts, it is more akin to their creative output, where they could design their own country or town based on the novel’s subject. The imaginative setting expands the limits of reality and invites the readers to explore the abstract, the symbolic, and the fantastical elements. One of the main advantages of an imaginative setting is that it provides a space where the conventional rules of time, space, and logic can be bent or broken. For instance, J.R.R. Tolkien’s Middle-earth, Lewis Carroll’s Wonderland, William Faulkner’s Yoknapatawpha, etc., all serve as the primary settings for all of their novels. Conversely, dystopian environments serve as a critique of authoritarian regimes and surveillance practices. For instance, George Orwell’s *1984* and Margaret Atwood’s *The Handmaid’s Tale* illustrate this point. The fictional worlds depicted in these works reveal the risks inherent in human

society and the erosion of personal identity. This also heightens the emotional and psychological resonance of the story. Meanwhile, in Samuel Beckett's *Waiting for Godot*, one can observe a desolate and timeless backdrop that reflects the futility and absurdity of human life. Therefore, imaginative settings enhance literature by offering unique contexts for storytelling and critical analysis. Whether they are magical, dystopian, surreal, or symbolic, they create a memorable impact and expand our comprehension of both imaginary realms and our own reality.

Ecocriticism

The phrase "ecocriticism" is thought to have been first used by William Rueckert in 1978. It refers to the examination of the connection between literature and the environment through an interdisciplinary lens, which draws inspiration from American transcendentalism. In the UK, the analysis of literature and the environment is referred to as "green studies," which is influenced by romanticism. Ecocriticism is closely linked to ecology. The term "ecology" was introduced by Joseph Meeker in his book *The Comedy of Survival: Studies in Literary Ecology*. Ecology studies the relationships among living organisms, including humans, and their physical surroundings. Joseph Meeker defined the literary ecology as, "the study of biological themes and relationships which appear in literary works. It is simultaneously an attempt to discover what roles have been played by literature in the ecology of the human species" (Meeker 9). Human beings rely on nature for essential needs such as air, food, and water, just as nature relies on them. Therefore, this mutually beneficial relationship between humans and the natural world, along with everything within it, thrives and is safeguarded when humans recognize environmental issues and work to resolve them for the benefit of nature. When ecocritics analyse a piece of literature, they explore how nature is portrayed and seek answers to questions like how the physical setting influences the representation of nature, how literature shapes

human interactions with the environment, and whether the values present in that artistic work align with ecological principles.

In literature, often nature serves as a metaphor for human moods and themes. It symbolizes various concepts ranging from beauty to chaos. For instance, in Arnold's "Dover Beach," one could witness the sea's significant role, like setting a mood, symbolizing human life and emotions, serving as a metaphor for faith, and finally mirroring the dual nature of life that is peace and the reality of uncertainty. The writers of the Romantic era had used nature to underscore the individualism and self-reflection. Hence, the narratives set in nature provide how the characters in the novel are related to the environment by revealing aspects of their personality.

Wessex: A Realm of Memory, Loss and Sufferings

Wessex was one of the kingdoms that comprised Anglo-Saxon England. The term "Wessex" is derived from the Old English version of "West Saxon." This kingdom is believed to have been established around 494 AD by Saxon invaders in Britain. Today, it has evolved into what is known as the West Country, a loosely defined region in southwest England, typically including the counties of Cornwall, Devon, Dorset, Somerset, and Bristol, with some people considering it to encompass all or parts of Wiltshire, Gloucestershire, and Herefordshire. Thomas Hardy, who was born in Dorset, found inspiration in his local surroundings, and he crafted an imaginative Wessex filled with numerous rural characteristics.

Tess from Hardy's *Tess of the d'Urbervilles* can be viewed as a representation of nature. Much like how nature selflessly safeguards humanity, Tess, as the eldest daughter in her family, also dedicates her life to caring for them. Her existence parallels the fluctuations of seasons, terrains, and the behaviour of animals. Considering how settings can influence the characters, Tess's life can be categorized into

two parts: first, her fortunes that align with the changing seasons, and second, the various locations that correspond with her different life phases. In this novel, Hardy employs seasonal changes not merely as a setting, but as a reflection and trigger for Tess's emotional state. The structure of the novel aligns with the natural farming calendar, and each transition between seasons symbolizes a psychological shift within Tess. For instance, Tess goes to the d'Urbervilles in the spring, when a lot of people begin looking for new jobs and working hard to sustain themselves. Tess's sorrowful journey starts in the spring, which marks the beginning of the full year. Alec abuses her sexually during the summer. Her decline continues into the fall of the year. After her distressing encounter with Alec, Tess departs from the d'Urberville residence with all she owns, and upon returning home, the approach of a dismal and bitter winter leaves her feeling deeply depressed. Tess gradually starts to recover, just as the environment around her. For most, Autumn is a season of harvest, when crops are ripening and harvests are plentiful, and people are busy collecting the products of their labour and celebrating a year of hard work. But autumn also brings with it a more subdued reality: brisk winds, bare trees, dropping temperatures, and the imminence of winter. The richness of the season is in stark contrast to Tess's predicament. The stunning beauty of the season contrasts sharply with Tess's difficulties. Even though she has some of her best times with Angel during this period, there is a harsh irony, her brief happiness is based on intense pain and ultimately brings to her demise. Winter, which represents both a beginning and an end, is the season she chooses for their wedding as well, that ultimately ends in tragic.

Hardy's locations are more than just beautiful scenery; they are active elements of the narrative that shape and mirror Tess's fate. These regions, which are located in his fictional Wessex, are equivalent to real locations in Dorset, Somerset, Wiltshire, and Devon; however, Hardy gives them symbolic meaning by giving them made-up names. Tess's birthplace of Marlott, which is modelled after

Marnhull in Dorset, is a remote that stands for her innocence and unadulterated rural roots. She first meets Alec in Trantridge, which becomes a source of moral danger and threat before she is assaulted. Inspired by the lush Frome valley close to Maiden Newton, Talbothays Dairy gives Tess her most hopeful and upbeat time, filled with the wonders of nature and the promise of love with Angel Clare. Conversely, Tess's physical exhaustion, emotional dejection, and the unrelenting nature of agricultural labour are all reflected in Flint comb-Ash, a hard upland farming area that is probably close to Puddletown Heath. Lastly, Sandbourne, based on the coastal town of Bournemouth, offers a superficial, genteel ease appealing yet detached from the pastoral environment that moulded her acting as the backdrop for her final desperate act. Collectively, these varied landscapes create a symbolic geography that tracks Tess's transformation from innocence to anguish and ultimately to tragedy, intertwining her emotional and moral journey with the natural and social contexts of Hardy's Wessex.

Area X: The Living Landscape

Jeff VanderMeer's Area X is an enigmatic, uninhabited territory filled with strange, unsettling landscapes and peculiar, often unclassifiable living creatures. When VanderMeer was inquired about the source of inspiration for the setting in *The Southern Reach*, has pointed to the marshes of North Florida, particularly the St. Marks Wildlife Refuge as the most similar real-world representation of Area X. Contrary to the typical perception of nature as vibrant, nurturing, and supportive of life, Area X depicts a version of the natural world that is alien, unpredictable, and transformative. In this manner, VanderMeer reconceptualizes nature as an independent, unfathomable force, one that pushes against the limits of what is known and what is not.

Jeff VanderMeer's *Annihilation* the first novel of *The Southern Reach Trilogy* narrates the journey of a biologist at the helm of an all-female team venturing into Area X, a bizarre and isolated

wilderness. While they navigate ever-changing terrains and disturbing life forms, the fabric of reality begins to break down. The Area X is enclosed by an unseen boundary, where flora and fauna undergo mutations, and time operates irregularly. The members of the expedition are strictly prohibited from using modern gadgets, “We had no cell or satellite phones, no computers, no camcorders, no complex measuring instruments” (VanderMeer 7). They quickly realise they lack both the terminology and the tools necessary to grasp Area X. A crucial element of this lack of understanding is the issue of scale: the area’s dimensions are unknown, and some of the beings within Area X are incomprehensibly massive.

The only individual who appears to have a unique outlook on Area X is ‘the biologist’. Her deep interest in nature and her readiness to embrace the new surroundings ultimately prevent her from perishing. At the start of the narrative, she was put under hypnosis by her colleague, the psychologist. When the expedition team chose to venture into the enigmatic "tunnel," which was not marked on their maps, the biologist accidentally breathed in a spore that altered her body, “the spores until I could see what long- term effects they might have on” (VanderMeer 27). After a while, when the psychologist attempted to hypnotize her again, she showed no response because the spore made her immune to it. She transformed into a being of enlightenment. She refers to the mysterious tunnel as a “tower”, “That night we talked about the tower, although the other three insisted on calling it a tunnel” (VanderMeer 12). Furthermore, she uncovered that the walls of the tower are alive and bear writings, “The words were composed of symbiotic fruiting bodies from a species unknown to me” (VanderMeer 26). For the biologist, Area X serves as a kind of sanctuary. In fact, she would happily choose to spend the rest of her life here. She is profoundly struck by the bizarre landscape of Area X. In her view, Area X represents land that is entirely pure and untarnished, filled with raw beauty. She observes, “The air was so clean, so fresh, while the world back beyond the border was what it had always been during the modern era: dirty,

tired, imperfect, winding down, at war with itself” (VanderMeer 30). She has completely devoted herself to Area X.

The slow deterioration of human identity, beginning with deliberate institutional suppression and progressing to ecological unification, has also been shown by VanderMeer. Crucially, the impact of the environment is closely associated with this breakdown of self. Area X is a dynamic, changing force that affects the protagonists, erasing their sense of self and changing them into something other than human, rather than just serving as a static background for human behaviour. Before the team ever sets foot in Area X, this metamorphosis is already underway. All personal identities are eliminated by the Southern Reach organization, which instead gives its members functional titles: “They took away our names in the month, stripped them from us. The only names applied to things in Area X, only in terms of their most general label” (VanderMeer 67). By removing names, the narrative deprives readers of a conventional emotional bond, mirroring the expedition participants’ experience of depersonalization.

The landscape itself threatens to undermine their identities as they enter Area X. The area is constantly changing; landmarks fade, paths vanish, and coastlines change, “The border is advancing... a little bit more every year,” the statement reads. (VanderMeer, 157). In normal settings, a sense of self and orientation are provided by stable geography; in these situations, instability causes uncertainty and weakens the mental frameworks that bind the self to known surroundings. Without trustworthy markers, the characters lose their psychological foundation in addition to their sense of direction.

Additionally, the ecosystem actively blends the lives of humans and nonhumans. interactions that are hybrid, such as “Then something more wrenching occurred. As they slid by, the nearest one rolled slightly to the side, and it stared at me with an eye that did not, in that brief flash, resemble a dolphin eye to me. It was painfully human, almost familiar” (VanderMeer 97), it diminishes the distinctions

between species, implying that the human singularity is fading. The biological impact of the environment is demonstrated by the biologist's own transition, which was brought on by breathing in spores: “The brightness within me flared up” (VanderMeer 144). She is able to connect with the nonhuman rhythms of Area X because of her metamorphosis, which is more than just a physical alteration.

Conclusion

The contrasting yet intertwined worlds of Hardy’s Wessex and VanderMeer’s Area X demonstrate how imagined landscapes serve as more than just literary settings; they are dynamic structures that embody philosophical inquiry, ecological consciousness, and cultural ideals. Hardy illustrates the mutually reinforcing relationship between human existence and the rural environment by grounding his characters in the cyclical rhythms of nature through his pastoral landscapes. VanderMeer’s scary wilderness, on the other hand, subverts human identity by presenting a world in which the nonhuman dominates and modifies the essence of life. However, both writers challenge readers to reconsider the traditional anthropocentric viewpoint, encouraging an awareness of the important influence of the environment on stories and human experience. Their works highlight the enduring significance of ecocritical perspectives in literature’s role in reflecting and modifying humanity’s relationship with the natural world by depicting nature as an agent of change, whether in a balanced or unsettling manner.

Works-cited

1. Hardy, Thomas. *Tess of the D'Urbervilles*. 2017th ed., Fingerprint Classics.
2. Li, Bin. "On The Natural Environment in *Tess of the D'Urbervilles* an Environment and Character Novel." *Universe Scientific Publication*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2022.
3. Md. Nuruzzaman. "Tess in Hardy's *Tess of the D'Urbervilles*: The Other Self of Nature." *Crossings*, vol. 7, 2017.

-
4. Meeker, Joseph W. “The Comedy of Survival: Studies in Literary Ecology.”
Leonardo, vol. 9, no. 4, Jan. 1976, p. 352. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1573415>.
 5. M.H. Abrams. *A Glossary of Literary Terms*. 11th ed., CENGAGE Learning, 2015.
 6. Mundy, Morgan. “Nothing Monstrous Existed Here: Uncanny Nature in The Southern Reach Trilogy.” *University of Mississippi eGrove*, Jan. 2019,
egrove.olemiss.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2103&context=hon_thesis
 7. The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica. “Wessex | Kingdom, History, Map, and Facts. *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 20 June 2025,
www.britannica.com/place/Wessex-historical-kingdom.
 8. Wagner, Wendy. “Interview: Jeff VanderMeer - Lightspeed Magazine.” *Lightspeed Magazine*, 20 May 2014,
www.lightspeedmagazine.com/nonfiction/interview-jeff_vandermeer.
 9. Tang, None He, and None Chen Xi. “On The Sea Image in Dover Beach.” *Journal of Literature and Art Studies*, vol. 12, no. 8, Aug. 2022,
<https://doi.org/10.17265/2159-5836/2022.08.002>
 10. VanderMeer, Jeff. *Annihilation*. 2014th ed., Harper Collins.